

Table 1. Searcher strategy in databases

Databases	Research Strategy	Limits	Filters
Medline (EBSCO)	(physical education OR physical fitness OR physical activity) AND (cognitive performance OR academic performance OR attention OR executive function OR memory) AND (children OR childhood)	Publication date: 2008-2018 English language <u>Age: 6-12 years</u> Free full text	4975
Pubmed	(physical education OR physical fitness OR physical activity) AND (cognitive performance OR academic performance OR attention OR executive function OR memory) AND (children OR childhood)	Publication date: 01/01/2008-12/31/2018 Humans Age: 6–12 years. English language Linked full text	1694
Eric Proquest	(physical fitness OR physical education OR physical activity) AND (cognitive performance OR academic performance OR attention OR executive function OR memory) AND (children OR childhood)	Publication date: 01/01/2008-12/31/2018 English language Journal Articles Elementary education	136
Web of Science	((physical education' OR 'physical activity' OR 'physical fitness') (cognitive performance' OR 'academic performance' OR attention OR executive function OR memory) (children OR childhood))	Publication date: 2008-2018 English language Articles Open access	1286